

SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF FAMILIES RAISING CHILDREN WITH SPECIAL EDUCATION NEEDS AND SOCIETY'S ATTITUDE TOWARDS THEM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7466176>

Abstract: In this article, information is provided about the relations in society to children with special education needs, the level of awareness, attention, and social adaptability of society to them. Recommendations for proper organization of family and community relations in child education are also presented.

Key words: disabled children, society, family, neighborhood, educational institution, special pedagogy, methodology.

Man is actually born for happiness and goodness, he lives with this hope. But the work does not end there, in order to achieve this intention, he must strive, show enthusiasm, and do good in order to see good. The family plays an important role in the formation of a person, in finding his place in life, in gaining respect in the country, in embodying the rules of high morals. The family is a place in which a person who ensures the continuity of life is formed, ethnic culture, traditions, moral and national values are preserved and developed, the foundation of economic and spiritual life, which determines the development of society, is laid and strengthened. If the family is close and harmonious, peace and harmony will be achieved in the society, peace and stability will prevail in the state.

Increasingly, in practice, teachers of pre-school and school educational institutions are faced with children because some of their characteristics do not stand out with their peers in society. As a rule, it is not difficult for these children to gradually digest the class and class labor education program, so a long time ago the definition of "disabled children" from the dictionary of pedagogy is additional, but today it is not difficult for these children's education and education has become an urgent problem.

Almost every group argues that in educational institutions for raising children with special educational needs, there are children's population studies specialists, kindergarten and middle class, as well as children with disabilities. What it is, it will become clear after studying the characteristics of this modern child in detail. First of all, children with physical or mental disabilities are considered to prevent the successful development of the child's educational program. The category of children is very diverse: it includes children with speech, hearing, vision, musculoskeletal, complex mental disabilities and mental tasks.

As a rule, as a problem, special children, such as preschool age, are teachers and parents. Therefore, modern pre-school education is a widespread organization in the society of the integration of special children in the society. Usually, it is divided into two forms of integration: inclusive and comprehensive education of disabled children. Integrated education takes place under an inclusive, pre-school special group. Integration and inclusive education practice in traditional peer groups, pre-school forced by clinical psychologists rates, In children are more tolerant than adults, because the children's society is almost always the

work, so as a rule, children usually do not notice children who are not completely healthy "*Communication without borders*".

If you take a child to school, first of all, pay attention to the level of specialists. If the development of the pathology is strongly expressed, the assistance to disabled children will be the priority activity of the relevant Kindergarten staff. First of all, child-specific studies are being conducted on the basis of which educational psychologist plans and individual development cards are being developed. The basis of the study of the baby includes such things as an individual interview with parents, study of the medical record, examination of the mental and physical development of the child. Depending on the nature of the pathology, psychologists work in a particular situation. A team of teachers visiting a disabled child is familiar with the findings and the directions of individual education of a special student.

For a child with no developmental anomalies, the adaptation period usually continues with childbirth. Naturally, disabled school-aged children will have more complex and problematic adaptation to social conditions. These children are used for continuous care by their parents, and constant support from them. Due to the establishment of social relations with peers, full communication with other children works hard due to lack of experience. The lessons are a little slower and with difficulty special Children are drawing, applique, modeling and other favorite children: there are not enough skills to develop children's activities. Integration of children with disabilities in preschool society is a participatory practice, it is recommended first of all to carry out psychological education of students of groups of children with disabilities. The child will be more comfortable if the development of communication barriers and Fielding's shortcomings do not differ from other children who are developing normally.

Taking a child for a special social experience is a great challenge for teachers to work with disabled children. Usually developing peers tend to easily accept the knowledge and skills of the teacher, but the development of children with severe diseases requires a special educational approach. Organize and plan the work of a school that is visited by a disabled child, usually experts. Such children's educational program includes the determination of a separate approach for the child, additional departments, suitable for specific educational needs. It also includes the ability to expand the educational interval for the child outside the educational institution, which is especially important for children with socialization difficulties. The most important condition for the implementation of the educational function is the special educational needs of the child, which depends on the nature of the disease and its severity.

A difficult challenge for the staff of the school institutions is the students of the school with disabilities. The educational program of school-age children is much more complex compared to pre-school, so much attention is paid to individual cooperation of individual students and teachers. This is due to the fact that, in addition to socialization, the child's educational program must provide conditions for assimilation, compensate for developmental deficiencies. - taking into account the nature and level of the increased pathology, it will be possible to determine the direction of the corrective effect on a specific student.

Children with disabilities who attend school, because they have some experience in communicating with peers and adults, are many well-adjusted children to society when they start school. In the absence of relevant experience, students with disabilities have gone through a period of adaptation that is much more difficult. RB communication with other students can lead to separation of the student from the class team complicated by the

presence of the child's illness. School specialists involved in the problem of adaptation, develop a special adaptive route for a disabled child. What is clear from the moment of its implementation. The process includes teachers working with the class, child's parents, parents of other students, educational administration institutions, health workers, school psychologist and sociologist. after a certain period of time, usually 3-4 months, the disabled child actually leads to the fact that the disabled child is sufficiently adapted to the school community. This very educational program facilitates the process of further training and assimilation.

INTEGRATION OF CHILDREN WITH DISABLED CHILDREN IN SOCIETY FAMILY INTERACTION AND EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

an important role in improving the quality of the educational process of a disabled child given to his family. How parents and teachers closely organize cooperation depends on the special student. Parents of disabled children should be interested not only in the assimilation of educational materials for their son or daughter, but also in establishing a relationship of an equal child with their peers. A positive psychological attitude contributes to the success of the assimilation of the complete program materials. Involving parents in classroom life helps to create a psychological climate in the family and school, respectively, and the child's adaptation in the classroom is a minimal demonstration of complications.

PSYCHOLOGICAL SUPPORT ORGANIZATION FOR DISABLED CHILDREN

To develop an individual educational route for children with severe diseases, experts must take into account the child's educational psychologist, social worker, pathologist, and receive support in the preventive clinic. The psychological support of special school students includes psychological service spending and the formation of emotional and willful skills, the development of intellectual characteristics at the level, and a diagnostic study at the state level. rehabilitation measures are planned based on the analysis of diagnostic results. Corrective work with children, which may be of a different nature and complexity, is carried out taking into account the characteristics of the identified pathology, with limited opportunities. It is a prerequisite for the organization of psychological support for children with disabilities.

Traditionally, teachers work according to a certain model: explaining new materials, performing tasks on the subject and assessing the level of knowledge acquisition. This program is for students with multiple visual disabilities. What is this? Special Education methods tend to be described in professional training courses for teachers working with disabled children. The general scheme is approximately as follows:

- ❖ *consistent explanation of new materials;*
- ❖ *performing tasks honorably;*
- ❖ *the student's repetition of task instructions;*
- ❖ *provision of audio-visual training manuals;*
- ❖ *a special system for evaluating the level of educational achievements.*

Special assessment includes, first of all, the scale of the individual rating according to the child's progress and their efforts.

The Uzbek people are a young people by nature. Kindness to children, kindness, self-sacrifice are characteristic features of our people. Therefore, your parents should ensure that their children get a thorough education, acquire a profession according to their interests, and

follow the rules of etiquette! will create the necessary opportunities for them to know and follow them. Because the proper upbringing of a child in the family is the guarantee of building a society with a solid foundation. Child rearing is a comprehensive, long-lasting complex process, which has its own characteristics. This process begins with the suitability of the young man and the young woman for each other. The future parents' health, lineage, outlook, morals, compatibility of material and spiritual level, all-round readiness for marriage are important in having a child and raising it. Family harmony, well-rounded children are the guarantee of the strength and spiritual maturity of the society.

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